

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH IN THERMOPLASTIC WINDING

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KEYWORDS: filament winding, ILSS, thermoplastic, impregnation.

ABSTRACT

The interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) of hoop filament wound cylinders with *in situ* impregnated TufRov[®] 4588 glass fiber bundles with thermoplastic polymer is investigated. Cylinders are wound at winding speeds ranging from 30 to 60 meters per minute using Stamylan[®] polypropylene with and without the coupling agent Exxelor[™] PO 1020. A special designed impregnation device with convex rotating rolls carries out the impregnation of the fiber bundles. This device is able to overcome the trade off between speed and impregnation quality and can reach fiber bundle speeds of 65 meter per minute. Curved specimens are cut from the wound cylinders and tested. The ILSS-values show that the tension in the fiber bundle decreases if the rolls in the impregnation device are powered, which makes the device especially useful for filament winding where a low fiber bundle tension and high speeds are required. The impregnation quality delivered by the current impregnation device is not yet optimal, which has its reflection on the relatively low ILSS-values compared to a maximum value of 22 MPa reported in literature. However, this study revealed the problem of impregnation with the current impregnation device and showed its potential for filament winding.

INTRODUCTION

The filament winding process becomes economically attractive if the production volume and level of automation is very high and the product is well designed [1]. Filament wound products exhibit a high level of reproducibility and strength over weight ratio, e.g. required for pressure vessels, especially in automotive and aerospace industry where weight is an important design parameter. The filament winding technique is also used for the production of sports equipment, such as hockey sticks, bicycle forks, masts for sailing and oars for whitewater rafting. Replacing conventional materials as metals and wood by filament wound products increases the strength and lowers the

weight of the product. Up till now, in the most filament winding processes thermoset materials are used for the impregnation of fiber bundles. This is because of their low viscosity, which makes impregnation of fiber bundles relatively easy. In general, no complex technological equipment is necessary for thermoset impregnation. However, main drawbacks of thermoset filament winding are a long curing time of the product and the limitation in fiber placement on the mandrel. Placing the product in an oven can decrease the curing time, but this requires extra action, equipment and energy. In some cases, the process of curing of the products may take place in the winding machine itself, so that it obstructs the winding of the following product. The freedom of placement of the fiber bundles on the mandrel is restricted to geodesic fiber paths or small deviations from this geodesic fiber path. The low friction between fiber bundle and previous layer easily results in slip and inaccurate fiber placement.

The application of thermoplastic materials instead of thermoset material decreases processing time significantly, since the material only has to solidify by cooling to get a ready product. Besides, thermoplastic material often has a higher toughness. Thermoplastic filament winding opens the way to the production of complex filament wound products, because of the so-called online consolidation.

Fig. 1 Prototype of an impregnation device for thermoplastic polymers with powered convex rolls (length 40cm).

This implies that the thermoplastic impregnated fiber bundle or tape actually “freezes” to the previously wound layer, allowing in this way for relatively large deviations from the geodesic line without the occurrence of slip. In this way, the fiber orientation becomes a design parameter, which can be engineered.

The main problem in thermoplastic winding is to achieve an economical winding speed and at the same time a high quality product. This problem arises from the high viscosity of molten thermoplastic material hampering impregnation, which is much higher than thermoset material, and the fact that the thermoplastic material must be heated to become fluid. Basically, there are two concepts in thermoplastic filament winding; the first is the use of pre-impregnated tapes, strands or prepregs, the second involves the *in situ*

impregnation of fiber bundles or tapes. Disadvantage of the first method is that the thermoplastic material must be heated, which results in low and uneconomical winding speeds. Attempts have been made by heating with flames, infrared, laser and hot air, but the winding speed remains low, where the best results in terms of winding speed are in the order of 5 meter per minute [5,6]. Besides, pre-impregnated materials are expensive. The *in situ* impregnation does not have the heating problem and is cheaper, but now the impregnation of fiber bundles or tape becomes an important issue. If the impregnation is done in the simplest way by guiding the fiber bundle through a bath with molten thermoplastic material, the impregnation quality will dramatically drop with increased fiber bundle or tape speed. This is normally referred to as the speed/quality dilemma. The simplest solution would be the use of a low viscosity thermoplast, but these materials tend to show a brittle behavior. This implies the need for an impregnation device, which is able to overcome the

quality/speed dilemma. The application of static cylindrical spreader pins increases the impregnation quality, but due to the frictional force between the fiber bundle and pins, and the effect of viscous shear stresses in a thin layer between fiber bundle and pin the tension in the fiber bundle is increased [7]. Further raising the speed finally leads to exceeding the maximum allowable stress in the fiber bundle, resulting in breakage.

In the present research, a prototype impregnation device for fiber bundles is constructed which has powered rotating rolls to reduce the viscous shear stresses and friction with the fiber bundle. The rolls have a tapered convex shape and are suspended at one side only, the coupling between the rolls is provided by chains. The convex shape is chosen to improve fiber bundle spreading, facilitating in this way impregnation. The one side suspension allows the automatic removal of eventually broken filaments. See Figure 1 for a picture of the impregnation device, which is called 'Rollerbox'. It has been demonstrated that this device can overcome the speed/quality dilemma [2] and is already able to achieve processing speeds up to 65 meter per minute. Up till now, the 'Rollerbox' has not been used in a manufacturing process.

The objective of the present work is to investigate the quality of filament wound products using the 'Rollerbox' for *in situ* impregnation. The effectiveness of the impregnation device is determined by performing an interlaminar shear strength (ILSS) test. This test provides information about both the impregnation quality of the fiber bundles and the bonding between the layers in the filament wound product. In the present study hoop wounded cylinder made of Stamylen[®] polypropylene with TufRov[®] 4588 glass fiber bundles with and without the coupling agent Exxelor[™] PO 1020 are produced. Exxelor[™] PO 1020 is used to improve the bonding between glass fibers and matrix. Cylinders are wound at fiber bundle speeds ranging from 30 to 60 meters per minute with or without using the powered rolls in the impregnation device in order to investigate the influence on the thermoplastic winding process.

PROCESS OF THERMOPLASTIC WINDING

The impregnation device called 'Rollerbox' is used in a test set-up for *in situ* thermoplastic filament winding. A schematic process overview can be found in Figure 2. The glass fibers are unwound from the inside of the bobbin and guided through a teflon (PTFE) guidance eye. The fiber bundle sizing is then broken by a device made of three teflon rolls, which should loosen the filaments in the fiber bundle in order to improve the impregnation process. An extra effect of this spreader device is that a pre-tension in the fiber bundle is build up, which is also beneficial for the impregnation process [9]. The fiber bundle enters the impregnation device through an inlet-die and passes over the four powered impregnation rolls and finally leaves the impregnation device by an outlet die. The impregnated fiber bundle is directly placed on the cylindrical mandrel in the 3-axes winding machine by a pay-out eye. A single screw extruder delivers the molten thermoplast to the heated impregnation device. The motor of the impregnation device, extruder and winding machine are controlled by a computer. For relatively low winding speeds a hot air blower is mounted on the pay-out eye pointing at the location where the fiber bundle is placed on the previous layer. This is done because the impregnated fiber bundle loses too much heat at low winding speeds caused by the distance between impregnation device and winding machine.

Fig. 2 Schematic overview of the thermoplastic winding test set-up

INTERLAMINAR SHEAR STRENGTH TEST

The interlaminar shear strength test, or briefly ILSS-test, is a short beam three point bending experiment for fiber reinforced plastics which determines the apparent shear strength between the layers and hence provide data about the impregnation quality of the material.

Specimens

The size of the filament wound cylinders did not allow for the application of an international standard norm. Instead, the dimensions for the present specimens are constructed from the standard norms ISO 4585 and ASTM D2344 and are depicted in Figure 3.

Fig. 3 Dimensions of the curved ILSS-specimens

The specimen is supported by two cylindrical shaped supports mounted on a Zwick 1484. A loading pin with a radius of 5 mm is lowered with a constant velocity of 1 mm per minute. The ILSS-test is valid if the failure mode occurs in shear between layers; see Figure 4 for valid failure modes. The maximum shear stress is calculated from the maximum force at which the first drop in this force is recorded under constant loading velocity.

Fig. 4 Valid failure modes for the ILSS-test

Calculation of the maximum shear stress

The maximum shear stress in a straight beam of homogeneous material loaded by a maximum load F_{\max} is estimated by

$$\tau_{\text{straight}}^{\max} = \frac{3F_{\max}}{4bt}, \quad (\text{Eq. 1})$$

where b and t are the width and thickness of the beam, respectively. Since in the present work curved specimens are used, the question arises whether it is still valid to use Eq.1. Fox [4] solved the nonlinear, three-dimensional equilibrium equations for through thickness shear, where slowly in-plane variation of the shell curvature and a small thickness over radius ratio is assumed. The through-thickness shear stress in a curved beam of homogeneous material in two dimensions without body forces is given by [4]

$$\tau_{\text{curved}} = \frac{1}{1+k\xi} \left(\frac{4k}{t^3} \xi^3 - \frac{6}{t^3} \xi^2 - \frac{k}{t} \xi + \frac{3}{2t} \right) \frac{V}{b}, \quad (\text{Eq. 2})$$

where V is the internal shear force, ξ the through thickness coordinate ranging from $-t/2 \leq \xi \leq t/2$ and k the curvature of the mid-plane, see Figure 5.

Fig. 5 Geometry of a curved beam specimen

The internal shear force depending on the coordinate α running along the mid-plane for frictionless support is given by

$$V(\alpha) = \frac{F \cos \alpha}{2 \cos \theta} \quad \text{for } 0 \leq \alpha \leq \theta \quad (\text{Eq. 3})$$

which yields for $\alpha=0$ the maximum shear force

$$V_{\max} = \frac{F}{2 \cos \theta}. \quad (\text{Eq. 4})$$

The equation governing the location of the maximum shear stress in a curved beam is obtained by differentiation to ξ of Eq. 2

$$\frac{\partial \tau_{\text{curved}}}{\partial \xi} = 0. \quad (\text{Eq. 5})$$

Next Eq. 5 is solved for ξ and the result is substituted together with Eq. 4 into Eq. 2. Figure 6 shows the influence of the radius of the mid-plane, normalized by the thickness, on the maximum shear

Fig. 6 Influence of the radius of a beam, normalized by the thickness, on the maximum shear stress.

formula is 7%. Hence, the maximum shear stress of the specimens in the ILSS-test is calculated based on Eq. 2.

stress in a curved beam compared to a straight beam for the geometry listed in Figure 3. Notice that for small radii the assumption of small thickness to radius ratio is violated too much. It can be seen that for small radii the influence on the shear stress is significant, but for larger radii the formula for straight beams can be applied. For the specimens in the present study the difference in maximum shear stress with respect to the straight beam

Temperature impregnation device	300	°C
Temperature melt extruder nose	290	°C
Diameter outlet die	2	mm
Distance outlet-die – pay-out eye	3700	mm
Pay-out eye width	2	mm
Winding angle cylinders	89.8	°
Temperature hot air gun (2000 W)	250	°C

Table 1 Process parameters for *in situ* thermoplastic winding

EXPERIMENTS

The test program consists of the hoop winding of cylinders at 30, 40, 50 and 60 meter per minute with and without rotating impregnation rolls in the impregnation device. The speed of the rolls in impregnation device is adjusted in such a way that the speed at the surface of the rolls at the largest radius is equal to the velocity of the fiber bundle, notated as $r_f=1$. Fixed impregnation rolls are defined by $r_f=0$. Notice that for $r_f=1$ there are still relative speed differences between fiber bundle and roll, because of the fiber bundle trajectory over the convex shaped impregnation rolls. From each cylinder four specimens are cut using a diamond saw according to the dimensions specified in Figure 3. The test program is performed for two types of material; TufRov[®] 4588 glass fiber bundles with Stamyln[®] 112MN40 polypropylene and TufRov[®] 4588 glass fiber bundles using Stamyln[®] and 5% of mass of Exxel[™] PO 1020, which is a coupling agent intended to improve the bonding between glass fibers and polypropylene. The throughput of the single screw extruder is set in such a way that the impregnation device is always filled. This can be verified by a hole in the impregnation device, which allows for overflow. The process parameters for thermoplastic winding are listed in Table 1. The pay-out eye width is the distance between the teflon (PTFE) rolls forming the pay-out eye. Teflon is used to prevent sticking and accumulation of thermoplast during the

process. A hot air gun is used for extra heat in the filament winding process at 30 meter per minute because of the large distance between impregnation device and winding machine.

Fig. 7 Mean maximum shear stress for curved ILSS-specimens from TufRov® 4588 glass fiber bundles and Stamyln® polypropylene with error bounds.

Fig. 8 Mean maximum shear stress for curved ILSS-specimens from TufRov® 4588 glass fiber bundles, Exxelor PO 1020 and Stamyln® polypropylene with error bounds.

Results

For each cylinder four specimens are tested and average values are presented. All the specimens failed in a valid failure mode for the ILSS-test. The mean ILSS-values as a function of the winding speed, including error bounds can be found in Figure 7 for the combination of TufRov® 4588 glass fiber bundles and Stamyln®. In Figure 8 the results are displayed if 5 mass percent of coupling agent Exxelor™ PO 1020 is added. The results for both material types are combined in Figure 9.

From these figures the following can be observed:

- In general, the ILSS-values are low compared to the values which may be expected for glass fibers with polypropylene based on literature. Scholtens and Brackman [10] report for glass fibers with a PP-incompatible film former an ILSS-value of 11 MPa, where for optimal conditions, i.e. the suitable product for matrix-fiber adhesion a value of 22 MPa is found. However, in Henninger *et al.* [9] the ILSS-values are of the order of 7 MPa for glass fibers with polypropylene for winding speeds up to 15 meter per minute where the glass fibers are also impregnated *in situ* by making use of a porous impregnation wheel. Above a winding speed of 15 meters per minute their ILSS-values decrease dramatically. In our case the maximum winding speed is four times higher.
- For both material types there is a trend that the ILSS-values are higher if the functionality of the rotating rolls in the impregnation device is not used. This is caused by the fact that the tension in the fiber bundle is higher which increases the compaction pressure in the filament winding process and hence improves the bonding between the layers.
- The ILSS-values increase if winding speeds also increase, except for the cylinders made from glass fibers and polypropylene at 40 meter per minute. This drop in ILSS-value could

Fig. 9 Mean maximum shear stress for curved specimens made of TufRov[®] 4588 glass fiber bundles and Stamylan[®] polypropylene with and without Exxelor PO 1020.

be explained by the fact that no hot air gun is used for cylinders wound above 30 meters per minute. However, this effect is not present for the specimens with the coupling agent. The reason that the ILSS values are generally higher at high winding speeds is that the impregnated fiber bundle has a higher temperature in the filament winding process, which is beneficial for the bonding with the previous layer.

- The application of Exxelor[™] PO 1020 indeed improves the bonding between matrix and glass fibers. Also, the failure of the specimens is more pronounced in terms of drop of force during constant velocity of the loading pin during tests.

Impregnation

The fracture surfaces of the ILSS-specimens reveal a lot of non-impregnated filaments. Non-impregnated filaments have already been observed at the inside of all the filament wound cylinders before preparation of the specimens. These two observations imply that the impregnation of the fiber bundle is far from ideal yet. The ideal situation would be that each individual filament is surrounded by matrix material and that the fiber content is large compared to the matrix content. A cross section of a cylinder made at 60 meter per minute is polished and investigated by light microscopy. The surface is treated with a coloring agent, in our case a red marking pen for white boards. The coloring agent penetrates into the spaces between the filaments and voids. By cleaning the surface carefully with alcohol, the voids and non-impregnated filaments can be observed. This method is described by Peltonen and Järvelä [11]. A picture of a typical cross section is shown in Figure 10, where clearly the individual fiber bundle can be observed with a large area of non-impregnated filaments in the core of the fiber bundle. This observation is no exception and is representative for all the specimens implying that indeed the impregnation quality of the impregnation device must be improved.

Fig. 10 Magnified picture (50x) of a polished surface of a cross section of a filament wound cylinder with *in situ* impregnated TufRov® 4588 glass fiber bundles with Stamyln® polypropylene at 60 meter per minute and $r_f=1$. An individual fiber bundle can be discerned with a core of non-impregnated filaments.

CONCLUSIONS AND DISCUSSION

The ILSS-values obtained in the present study in thermoplastic winding using our prototype impregnation device are of the same order as reported in Henninger *et al.* [9] using a porous impregnation wheel. However, in our case winding speeds were used up to 60 meter per minute, where in [9] the ILSS-values already drop dramatically at a winding speed of 15 meter per minute. A winding speed of 60 meter per minute is a really economically viable speed for industrial application. It should be noted that the work by Henninger *et al.* [9] is the only other paper facing the problem of obtaining economic speeds for thermoplastic winding. All other publications mention much lower speeds. Still, compared to the ILSS-value obtained by Scholtens and Brackman [10] of 22MPa under ideal conditions the *in situ* thermoplastic filament winding process must be improved. These improvements must be done on two points in the process; the first is the application of a consolidation roller to enlarge the compaction pressure and the latter the enhancement of the impregnation device.

In the filament wound specimens a lot of non-impregnated filaments were observed, indicating that the impregnation process is not yet ideal. Since the geometry of the current impregnation device is chosen based on workmanship, the development of a mathematical model featuring the principles of the current impregnation device is started [3]. This model will be used to find an optimized geometry for a new impregnation device with respect to impregnation quality.

ACKNOWLEDGEMENT

The authors would like to acknowledge DSM Research for the financial support. PPG Industries Fiber Glass in Hoogezand, the Netherlands, is thanked for supplying the TufRov® 4588 glass fiber bundles. The coupling agent Exxelor™ PO 1020 for glass fibers and polypropylene was kindly provided by Exxon Mobile Chemical, Benelux.

REFERENCES

1. M. Bannister, "Challenges for composites into the next millennium – a reinforcement perspective", *Composites Part A: applied science and manufacturing*, 32, 901-910, 2001.
2. R. Marissen, L.T. van der Drift and J. Sterk, "Technology for rapid impregnation of fiber bundles with a molten polymer", *Composites Science and Technology*, 60, 2029-2034, 2000.
3. T. Weustink, F. van Keulen and R. Marissen, "Virtual prototyping of an impregnation device with convex rolls", *Proceedings ECCM-10 Conference, Composites for the Future*, June 3-7, Brugge, Belgium, 2002.
4. D.D. Fox, "Transverse shear and normal stresses in nonlinear shell theory", *Computers & Structures*, 75, 313-319, 2000.
5. F. Rosselli, M.H. Santare and S.I. Guçeri, "Effects of processing on laser assisted thermoplastic tape consolidation", *Composites Part A*, 28A, 1023-1033, 1997.
6. P. Klein, P. Reinicke, F. Hauptert and K. Friedrich, "Winding of extruded thermoplastic tapes by using a hot air source", *Flow Processes Compos. Mater., Proc. Int. Conf.*, 5th, 63-69, 1999.
7. P.J. Bates and J.M. Charrier, "Pulling tension monitoring during the melt impregnation of glass roving", *Polymer Composites*, 21:1, 104-113, 2000.
8. F. Henninger and K. Friedrich, "Thermoplastic filament winding with online-impregnation. Part A: process technology and operating efficiency", *Composites Part A*, 33, 1479-1486, 2002.
9. F. Henninger, J. Hoffmann and K. Friedrich, "Thermoplastic filament winding with online-impregnation. Part B. Experimental study of processing parameters", *Composites Part A*, 33, 1677-1688, 2002.
10. B.J.R. Scholtens and J.C. Brackman, "Influence of the film former on fibre-matrix adhesion and mechanical properties of glass-fibre reinforced thermoplastics", *Journal of Adhesion*, 52, 115-129, 1995.
11. P. Peltonen and P. Järvelä, "Methodology for determining the degree of impregnation from continuous glass fibre prepreg", *Polymer Testing*, 11, 215-224, 1992.